

SUBSEQUENT VALUATION OF PROPERTY, PLANT AND EQUIPMENT

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Abstract: The problems of fixed assets and a technique of audit of fixed assets in accordance with international standards were considered in the article. Review of regulatory framework of accounting and audit of fixed assets was conducted. Fixed assets' criteria and features of recognition have been considered. The principles and requirements IAS 16 «Fixed Assets» were outlined in article. The solutions in accordance of problems were revealed under international standards.

Key words: accounting, auditing, fixed assets, tangible assets, depreciation, inventory, international standards, property, plant and equipmen

Introduction. Subsequent assessment of fixed assets according to international standards. IAS 16 provides for two models for the subsequent measurement of property, plant and equipment:

- 1) the cost model.
- 2) the revaluation model.

When selecting the first model, fixed assets after recognition

they are carried at cost less accumulated depreciation and impairment losses. The second model assumes that, after recognition, property, plant and equipment are carried at a revalued amount, which is their fair value at the date of revaluation, less accumulated depreciation and impairment losses.

When choosing the second model, revaluations of items of property, plant and equipment should be carried out regularly so that their carrying amount does not differ significantly from the fair value at the reporting date. The frequency of revaluations is not limited and depends on changes in the fair value of property, plant and equipment. The fair value of certain categories of property, plant and equipment may fluctuate significantly, so they require annual revaluation. Property, plant and equipment with minor changes in fair value may be revalued every three to five years.

The amount of the increase in the carrying amount of an item of property, plant and equipment as a result of revaluation is recognized in other comprehensive income (other comprehensive income, depending on the conversion) and accumulated in equity under the heading "Revaluation surplus". However, such an increase should be recognized in profit or loss to the extent that it compensates for the amount of the revaluation decrease of the same asset previously recognized in profit or loss.

The amount of the decrease in the carrying amount of an item of property, plant and equipment as a result of revaluation is included in profit or loss, unless it can be deducted directly from the corresponding item of other comprehensive financial result (the item "Revaluation surplus" in equity), to the extent that it does not exceed the amount of this item obtained as a result of a previous revaluation of the same item of property, plant and equipment.

IAS 16 provides for mandatory depreciation of items of property, plant and equipment in the event of an impairment. The procedure for determining the amount of depreciation of an item of property, plant and equipment is regulated by IAS 36 (IAS) "Impairment of Assets", according to which the carrying amount of an asset should be reduced to its recoverable amount if the latter is less than the carrying amount. The carrying amount is the amount at which an asset is carried after deducting accumulated depreciation and impairment losses. The recoverable amount is defined as the largest of the two values: 1) the fair value of the asset less the cost of selling it, and 2) the value of its use. In this case, the value in use is defined as the discounted (present) value of the cash flows expected from the continued use of the asset and from its disposal at the end of its useful life. In turn, the estimate of future cash flows from the use of the asset is based on forecasts. Due to the fact that the forecast is made for a fairly long period (usually up to five years), the estimate of future cash flows should be discounted. The discount rate should reflect the assessment of the time value of money and the risks specific to the asset.

The reduction in the value of assets may be affected by:

- * * significant changes in technology;
- * * significant changes in economic conditions;
- * * obsolescence of the asset;
- * * physical damage to the asset;
- * * changes in market conditions, etc.

In accordance with IAS 36, at each date of the financial statements, the company must assess whether there is any indication that an item of property, plant and equipment may be impaired, which includes the following::

- • during the reporting period, the market value of the asset decreased significantly more than expected;
- * * significant changes in technological, economic or legal conditions occurred or are expected to occur in the near future during the reporting period;
- * there have been significant changes in the discount rate used to determine the recoverable amount of the asset;
- * there is evidence of obsolescence of the asset or its physical damage;
- * a number of other features.

The presence of any of these indicators indicates that the company's financial statements should reflect the impairment of the asset. In accordance with IAS 36, the amount of an asset's impairment is determined by comparing its carrying amount and its recoverable amount. If the recoverable amount is less than the carrying amount, the financial statements recognize an impairment of the asset and its carrying amount is reduced to the recoverable amount. The amount of the decrease in the carrying amount when an item of property, plant and equipment is impaired should be recognized in profit or loss in the current period (as an expense), unless it can be attributed to a reduction in other comprehensive financial result (other comprehensive income) resulting from a previous revaluation of the item.

We will comment on the regulations of IAS 36 on accounting for impairment of assets in the following example.

Example 4.3

On the balance sheet of the organization "Alfa" there are computer equipment, the initial cost of which is 100,000 sums, accrued depreciation — 10,000 sums. Some signs (significant changes in technology, obsolescence compared to other similar fixed assets) indicate their obvious impairment. For example, the fair value

of the specified computer equipment is 72,000 sums. Expenses related to the sale of the above-mentioned equipment, 2000 sums. Based on the forecasts of the receipt of funds from the further use of the specified equipment in the organization

"Alfa" calculated the value of its use, which amounted to 60,000 sums.

The fair value of computer equipment, minus the cost of selling it, is 70,000 sums (72,000 sums — 2000 sums). The recoverable amount of computing equipment, calculated as the higher of the fair value of the asset less the cost of selling it (UZB 70,000) and the value in use of the asset (UZB 60,000), is UZB 70,000. The carrying amount of the object (initial cost less accumulated depreciation) is 90,000 sums (100,000 sums — - 10,000 sums).

Since the recoverable amount of an item of property, plant and equipment was less than its carrying amount, an impairment of computer equipment should be recognized in the financial statements. The carrying amount of the asset should be adjusted to the recoverable amount, with the amount of the impairment loss attributed to profit or loss (as an expense). The impairment loss in our example will be 20,000 sums. (90,000 sums — 70,000 sums).

Subsequent valuation of fixed assets in accordance with Russian accounting regulations. In accordance with PBU 6/01, the initial cost of fixed assets is not subject to change, except in cases established by the legislation of the Russian Federation. Changes in the original cost of fixed assets are allowed in cases of completion, retrofitting, modernization, reconstruction, partial liquidation and revaluation of fixed assets. Commercial organizations have the right to revalue fixed assets at their current replacement cost no more than once a year. Thus, PBU 6/01 allows revaluation of fixed assets, therefore, the approach to their subsequent assessment in the domestic regulatory act generally corresponds to the approach to

this assessment in IAS 16. Similarly, IAS 16 PBU 6/01 provides for the regularity of revaluations, without limiting their maximum period. However, in contrast to IAS 16, PBU 6/01 sets a minimum revaluation period of one year for fixed assets. In addition, the overvalued value itself differs in Russian and international standards. In PBU 6/01, the current replacement cost category is used as such value, and in IAS 16, the fair value category is used. It should also be noted that in this RAS, the original cost of fixed assets is brought to the revalued value, and in IFRS — the carrying amount.

The procedure for accounting for revaluation of fixed assets in Russian and international standards is generally the same. According to PBU 6/01, the amount of revaluation of an item of property, plant and equipment is credited to the additional capital of the organization, which corresponds to the article "Revaluation surplus" used in IAS 16 in this situation as part of capital. In accordance with PBU 6/01, the amount of markdown of an item of property, plant and equipment is charged to the financial result as other expenses, which is consistent with the regulations of IAS 16 on the recognition of the amount of markdown in profit or loss in the current period as an expense.

The difference from IAS 16 is that PBU 6/01 does not require accounting for impairment of items of property, plant and equipment. PBU 6/01 does not provide for the procedure for calculating and accounting for markdowns of property, plant and equipment in the event of their impairment, nor does it use the recoverable amount category. Independently deciding on the revaluation of fixed assets, the head of the organization has the right not to reduce their carrying amount, even if they are obviously impaired.

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